

CREATIVITY AND SOCIAL ACTIVITY AS A FACTOR OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The article reflects the elements of the professional and personal, theoretical and practical component of pedagogical activity, which are the measure and method of creative self-realization of the teacher.*

Keywords: *social activity, creativity, creative activity, creative innovative activity, competence, pedagogical skill, pedagogical ability.*

Reforming the existing education system in the course of implementing the Law "On Education" provides for the formation of a comprehensively developed socially active personality of a citizen through a system of continuous education, in which higher education occupies a special place.

In the period of market relations and innovative technologies, the requirements for pedagogical skills and professional competence of future teachers increase even more.

The qualitative and structural changes taking place in the system of higher education in the context of its modernization are ultimately aimed at the professional and personal development of students. We combine these two most important components of a specialist in the concept of "professional competence", giving this phenomenon a certain universal character, because we believe that it includes both professionalism, and skill, and creative innovation, and creative abilities, and high intelligence, and cultural - moral values, in a word, this is a certain desired image of a specialist who should be formed in the humanistic educational system of the university and with the greatest efficiency will be able to realize his human and professional potential in specific activities, constantly developing through self-education, self-education and self-improvement [1; S.395].

In the dynamics of modern educational processes, the fundamental importance of pedagogical professional competence is increasingly recognized, which is seen as a systemic, integrative unity, a synthesis of intellectual and practical skills. Such professional competence includes cognitive, functional and cultural unity in the content of teacher education. This also includes the personal characteristics of the teacher, such as value orientations, abilities, character traits, readiness to interact with children and carry out practical activities that allow a person to use his potential, carry out complex, culturally appropriate activities, quickly and successfully adapt to a constantly changing society and professional activities [2; S.72-75].

Therefore, today all participants in the educational process are faced with the problem of improving the quality of education and adapting it to the emerging realities of life. To determine the essential characteristics of innovative activity, it is advisable to consider it in the parameters of creativity. This is quite understandable, since it is traditional for pedagogical science to identify creative and innovative pedagogical activity, since the creativity of teachers serves as the engine of innovation.

Creativity, as an active independent activity, generates something new. Its novelty can be assessed from objective and subjective points of view. The most important feature of creative activity is the independent transfer of knowledge and skills to a new situation. It manifests itself in the fact that, solving some new problem for itself, the subject is able to use long-acquired knowledge and skills to find a solution. This is not always done, especially if the previously acquired knowledge lies in a different scientific field in relation to the problem being solved.

In the first case, the criterion is the social value and novelty of the solution, and here we can talk about creativity in the full sense of the word as the activity of an artist, scientist, inventor, teacher, etc. In the second case, the creative process does not have novelty and social significance, but nevertheless, in the process of creative activity, the same psychological processes that are characteristic of full-fledged forms of creativity can take place. This is explained by the fact that the subject of creativity in this case also makes discoveries, but for himself, and thus enriches his abilities, creativity and inner world as a whole. That is why the creative activity of students in a wide variety of manifestations becomes an important means for the successful development of many socially significant, creative qualities of a person (imagination, thinking, courage, determination, strong-willed qualities) and familiarization with such activities is considered by modern didactics as a necessary element of the content of education [3; S.370].

Famous scientists such as V.A.Kan - Kalik, Yu.P.Azarov, P.T.Magzumov, Kh.A.Turakulov, V.A.Slastenin, S.K.Annamuratova investigated certain aspects of this problem.

The pedagogical process in the general education system should stimulate activity, receiving an additional impetus, energy, for more intensive creative activity. Noteworthy in this regard are the judgments that "... today a lot of fruitful work is being done to equip the teacher with scientific knowledge in the field, the general and psychological and pedagogical training of the teacher is being improved. But, paradoxically, little attention is paid to improving the personality of the teacher, her ... natural qualities, the very human nature of the teacher, which the teacher himself is not aware of enough, is not always able to dispose of and manage it in various fields of activity"(V.A. Kan-Kalik) [4; S.573].

At the same time, "the skill of the teacher is not only in the fact that he must develop techniques, but in the fact that, each time dealing with new circumstances, with the changeable, not standing still, constantly developing nature of children, it becomes necessary to think in an original way, act without direct copying. (Yu.P. Azarov).

The creative process of the teacher is considered by scientists as "an activity aimed at constantly solving a countless number of educational tasks in changing circumstances, during which the teacher develops and implements in communication with children optimally, original for this pedagogical individuality, not standard pedagogical solutions, mediated by the characteristics of the object - subject of pedagogical influence" (V.A. Slastenin).

Mastery is the achievement of the highest results in a certain activity and the constant creative improvement of an employee in it, based on knowledge of the universal, general and particular laws and patterns of development of nature, society, thinking and their skillful application in practice.

Conditions for achieving professional, including pedagogical, **mastery**:

Use of one's own labor practice as a source of improvement of professional knowledge, skills and abilities;

1. The growth of practical activity in mastering the best methods of work, the constant complication of the professional tasks performed;
2. If necessary - the expansion of cognitive and practical activity beyond the limits of this specialty;
3. Studying and creative development of the advanced experience of colleagues, the introduction into the application of the previously obtained known and unique, which after some time may become public property;
4. Increasing the requirements for general educational, political, professional training, since without knowledge and their creative application in the labor process, it is impossible to form professional skills;
5. Love for your profession;
6. Work culture;
7. Search for the most productive methods of work, creativity, innovation.

Thus, by forming students' knowledge, skills and abilities, the teacher must unlock the potential of the participants in the educational process and provide them with the opportunity to display their creative abilities. The teacher must have a creative, pedagogical ability to develop both specific teaching goals for a particular group of students and professional training standards; should have the ability to select materials from a huge amount of information that best meet the learning objectives and provide the necessary level of knowledge, skills and abilities.

The components of pedagogical abilities include the following: constructive abilities - to design the student's personality, select and compositionally build educational material in relation to the age and individual abilities of students; **organizational skills** - to include students in various activities and make the team an instrument of influence on each individual; **communication skills** - to establish the right relationship with students and rebuild them in accordance with the development of goals and means; **gnostic abilities** - to explore the object, process and results of one's own activity and rebuild it on the basis of this knowledge.

A teacher can achieve a good result if he remembers that the program is for the students and not the students for the program; presents the material clearly, reasonably and systematically, while revealing the necessary and definite connections and dependencies; adapts the pace of learning to the needs of the majority of students, subject to individual work with lagging behind; uses rational forms of oral, written, computer control and skillfully corrects learning; interests students in achieving their maximum learning outcomes, at the same time developing their motivation for learning.

It can be confidently asserted that in the modern world there is a tendency to merge educational and information technologies and the formation on this basis of fundamentally new integrated learning technologies, based, in particular, on Internet technologies. With the use of such technologies, the possibility of unlimited and very cheap replication of educational information, its fast and targeted delivery has become possible. At the same time, learning becomes interactive, the importance of independent work of students increases, the intensity of the educational process is seriously increased, etc.

Consequently, students of higher educational institutions should master the basis of a new pedagogical methodology, study the rich spiritual, historical and educational heritage of the people, the latest pedagogical technology, be familiar with foreign progressive and practical ideas, cultivate spiritual and moral qualities, independent thinking.

Based on the fact that the teacher, in addition to scientific knowledge in the specialty, starting the educational process, must possess the sum of pedagogical and psychological knowledge, technology and teaching methods, the textbook provides for the study of the essence and basic concepts of professional pedagogical skill, the didactic foundations of its formation, psychological pedagogical theory of improving professional skills, ideas and experience of scientists and practitioners who have achieved outstanding success in the field of pedagogical skills, with the aim of creative application of these ideas and experience by future teachers in the formation of a system of their own experience that integrates the achievements of science and educational practice.

Thus, by forming students' knowledge, skills and abilities, the teacher must unlock the potential of the participants in the educational process and provide them with the opportunity to display their creative abilities. In this way, one of the tasks of modern education is realized.

An analysis of various sources on the problem of creativity in pedagogical science allows us to conclude that it characterizes the most important indicator of the social and professional maturity of a teacher, which manifests itself in such features as: the desire for constant professional, intellectual, cultural and moral self-improvement; interest in the success of the activity; the need for creative self-realization in work, search, originality, constructive thinking in relation to the world; the ability to find the best ways and means to eliminate shortcomings in order to achieve better performance, to foresee the consequences of one's actions and deeds; the ability to take responsibility for the results of their own activities, the team; the ability to independently vary, by methods and means to find ways to achieve the goals of their creative activity and social activity.

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